

In RTD-infected plants, RTBV DNA was detected in all parts of the infected plant by PCR. The PCR technique is much more sensitive than F(ab')₂ ELISA for

detecting the presence of RTBV in symptomatic and symptomless plant tissue.

Oligonucleotide primers were designed to the published sequence of RTBV. The

1. Viral coat proteins in different plant parts as detected by ELISA and PCR.

^a1 and 2 = leaves emerged before insect inoculation; 3 = newly emerged leaf after insect inoculation; NV = no virus (es) detected; B = RTBV; S = RTSV; B + S = RTBV + RTSV.

^b20 RTD-infected plants were dissected into five parts (leaves 1, 2, and 3, stem apex, and roots). ^cOut of 20 RTD-infected plants, dissected parts of two plants were tested by PCR.

plus strand primer (5'-GAG-CGCTGATTACCCAACCTTTCAAGG-3') and minus strand primer (5'-GGA-GTAGAATACTCCACAACCGGCG-3') were complementary to regions of the P12 and P194 open reading frames, respectively, and amplified an 827-bp fragment of RTBV DNA. PCR reaction conditions were standard with a typical input of 100 ng of total nucleic acid extract of rice plant tissue and 50 nM primers. PCR reaction products were resolved on 1% agarose gels stained with ethidium bromide (Fig. 2). ■

2. PCR products resolved in 1% agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide. Markers: lane 1 = uninfected extract; lane 2 = no DNA; lanes 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 = extracts from stem apex, dissected leaves no. 3, 2, 1, and roots.

Evaluation of resistance to bakanae and foot rot disease

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Bakanae and foot rot disease, caused by *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld., appeared in patches on Basmati 385 in farmers' fields during 1989. The disease developed further because no control measures were adopted. None of the Basmati 385 fields surveyed during 1991 were disease-free in Sheikhpura, Gujranwala, and Sialkot districts, which make up the traditional rice-growing area in the Punjab. Disease incidence ranged from 5 to 90%.

To overcome the disease problem through resistant varieties, 10 fine-grain and 10 medium-grain varieties/lines were screened in the greenhouse during 1990-92. Soil was infected with the diseased plant debris and *F. moniliforme* culture grown on wheat grains. During 1990 and 1992, the inoculum potential

Reaction of rice varieties/lines to bakanae and foot rot disease under greenhouse conditions.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)		
	1990	1991	1992
<i>Fine grain</i>			
Basmati 370	16.7	92.4	15.40
Basmati 6129	8.3	77.0	69.20
Basmati 198	0.0	38.5	54.6
Basmati 385	58.3	84.7	46.2
4048	50.0	100.0	61.5
1053-32	-	92.4	0.0
4439	-	15.4	0.0
1053-1-2	-	84.7	7.7
33608	-	100.0	7.7
Basmati C-622	16.7	100.0	46.2
<i>Medium grain</i>			
Shadab	0.0	0.0	0.0
Iran	-	92.4	30.8
PK3303-15-1	-	0.0	0.0
DR83	0.0	30.8	0.0
Jhona 349	-	100.0	38.5
IR8	-	0.0	0.0
IR6	0.0	7.7	0.0
IR9	0.0	0.0	0.0
KS282	0.0	0.0	0.0
PK1399-12-1-1-0-6	0.0	7.7	0.0

was kept low, while it was doubled in 1991 to test the resistance in the materials. Seedlings were transplanted at 40 d. Elongation/mortality of the seedlings started 2 wk later. Data were recorded 1 1/2 mo after transplanting (see table).

Among the fine-grain varieties/lines,

Basmati 370, 4439, 1053-1-2, 1053-32, and 33608 showed resistance under low inoculum potential and high incidence under high inoculum potential. These varieties can be grown in fields with low soil infestation. Basmati 385, Basmati 6129, and 4048 are susceptible under all

conditions and should be avoided. Medium-grain varieties/lines—IR6, IR8, IR9, Shadab, KS282, PK3303-15-1, and PK1399-12-1-1-0-6—were highly resistant and can be grown successfully in severely infested fields. ■

Pathological constraints on hybrid rice production technology

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Preliminary observations during 1989 kharif (monsoon) season revealed a higher incidence of *Fusarium sheath rot* (FShR), caused by *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld., and kernel smut *Tilletia barclayana* (Bref.) Sacc. & Syd. on cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines than on their corresponding maintainers. We have since been observing these diseases under natural field conditions at

Percent incidence of kernel smut on CMS lines and hybrid rice and their corresponding maintainers, restorers, and inbred rice varieties.* Kapurthala, India, 1991.

Entry	Incidence (%)	Incidence on corresponding maintainer line (%)
<i>CMS line</i>		
PMS1 A	9.5	0.7
PMS2 A	10.7	0.5
PMS3 A	15.0	0.5
PMS4 A	2.9	0.6
PMS5 A	4.8	1.2
PMS6 A	0.9	0.8
PMS7 A	4.6	1.0
PMS8 A	13.9	0.5
PMS9 A	0.5	1.0
PMS10 A	7.5	0.3
<i>Hybrid rice</i>		
PAU2 A/1126-1-1	5.8	
PMS8 A/1106-6-2	10.2	
PMS8 A/31432	5.1	
PMS8 A/1126-15-3	10.0	

*Kernel smut incidence was 0.05-1.7% on restorer lines and 0.08-0.68% on inbred rice varieties (grown next to CMS lines) PR106, PR108, PR109, Jaya, Basmati 370, and Basmati 385. Incidence in Pusa Basmati No. 1 was 1.3%.

Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, and at DSST research farms.

To assess FShR severity, we randomly selected 100 tillers at five nearly equally spaced spots in a seed production plot. Disease intensity was scored on a 0-4 scale where 0 = no infection and 4 = maximum infection where no panicle emerged.

We detected kernel smut by soaking 5,000 seeds of each sample in sodium hydroxide (0.2%) solution for 20 h at 25 °C. Seeds were then washed thoroughly and spread out on blotting paper for examination.

Kernel smut and FShR were generally more severe on CMS lines and hybrid rice compared with their corresponding maintainers, restorers, and inbred rice varieties (see table). Kernel smut incidence was as high as 9.5-15.0% in CMS

lines. FShR intensity was 33.1-42.4% in CMS lines and 15.4-19.3% in maintainers, restorers, and inbred rice varieties. Panicles of CMS lines are enclosed in sheaths longer than panicles of other types of rice plants, thus providing favorable conditions for disease development. Nonexsertion of CMS panicles was 11.2-16.8% compared with 2.4-5.8% in the other groups.

The high degree of susceptibility of CMS lines to FShR and kernel smut might become a limiting factor in hybrid seed production and perhaps commercial hybrid yields. Transferring genes imparting resistance or partial resistance to kernel smut to CMS lines might be useful. We are exploring the use of chemical seed treatment and foliar sprays to check the disease. ■

High-yielding, brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant varieties developed at Maruteru, Andhra Pradesh (AP), India

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Severe BPH damage that led to hopperburn was noticed in AP in 1976. Since then, BPH has been a recurring problem in both wet (WS) and dry (DS) seasons in rice areas of East and West Godavari, Krishna, and Guntur districts. Yield losses due to BPH have ranged from 10 to 100%.

Developing BPH-resistant varieties is environment friendly and offers economic savings for farmers. Resistant donors ARC6650 and ARC5984 and popular high-yielding local variety

Sowbhagya were used in a breeding program for BPH resistance that began in the late 1970s at ARS. Selection was exercised in segregating populations of crosses Sowbhagya/ARC6650 and Sowbhagya/ARC5984, resulting in the release of six promising BPH-resistant varieties during 1986-91 (see table).

Farmers of Krishna and Godavari deltas are growing these varieties during WS on 1 million ha. They were proven superior in several yield evaluation trials at state and national levels, including the All India Coordinated Trials. ■